

Spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods for determination of antiviral drug-ribavirin in its dosage forms and plasma

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Abstract : Two sensitive, accurate and precise spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods have been proposed and validated for the determination of the antiviral drug, ribavirin (RBV) in its dosage form and in plasma. Both methods were based on the condensation of RBV with 1,2-naphthoquinone-4-sulfonate (NQS) in an alkaline medium to form an orange-colored product. The spectrofluorometric method involved the reduction of that colored product with calcium hydride (CaH_2), and the subsequent measurement of the formed fluorescent product at 406 nm after excitation at 344 nm. The spectrophotometric method involved the measurement of the colored product at 452 nm. The optimum experimental conditions have been studied carefully. Linear relationships with good correlation coefficients (0.9993 and 0.9999) and LOD (0.02 and $1.48 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) were obtained in the ranges of 0.05–8.0 and 5.0–65.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for the spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods, respectively. Both methods were successfully applied to the determination of RBV in capsules. As its higher sensitivity, the spectrofluorometric method was applied to the determination of RBV in plasma. The results obtained by the proposed methods were comparable with those obtained by a reported method.

Keywords : Ribavirin, spectrofluorometry, spectrophotometry, capsules, spiked plasma samples.

Introduction

Ribavirin (1-*b*-D-ribofuranosyl-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-carboxamide) (Fig. 1), is a purine nucleoside analogue with broad spectrum activity against both DNA and RNA viruses. Ribavirin (RBV) is a hydrophilic molecule that does not bind to plasma proteins. It is an antiviral drug

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of ribavirin.

used by many hospitals in the treatment of respiratory syncytial virus infection. It is considered by some physicians to be an effective and sometimes life-saving drug,

but studies have also indicated that the drug may pose a reproductive risk to health care workers. It has since been found to be effective when used in combination with interferon-*a*-2*b* for the treatment of chronic hepatitis C. In several clinical trials, combination therapy of interferon plus ribavirin significantly enhanced end-of-treatment and sustained virological and biochemical response rates in treatment of experienced patients¹.

Several methods have been reported for the determination of ribavirin viz. high performance liquid chromatography^{2,3}, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry⁴⁻⁷, thin layer chromatography⁸, capillary electrophoresis⁹, chemiluminescence¹⁰, spectrophotometry^{11,12} and spectrofluorometry¹³. The reported spectrophotometric methods^{11,12} were based on the oxidation reaction of RBV by some oxidizing agents then coupling of the oxidation product in both methods with 3-methylbenzothiazolin-2-one hydrazone producing a deep blue color with maximum absorption wavelength at 630 nm, while the reported spectrofluorometric method¹³ was based on the oxidation of

RBV by cerium(IV) and measuring the fluorescence intensity of cerium(III) in perchloric acid medium at λ_{em} 355 nm after excitation at λ_{ex} 255.

Experimental

Reagents and materials :

All chemicals were of analytical grade, distilled water was used throughout the experiments. 1,2-Naphthoquinone-4-sulphonate, NQS; (El-Nasr Pharmaceutical Chemical Co., Abo-Zaabal, Egypt), calcium hydride, purity (95.0%) was purchased from Fluka (Switzerland). Sodium hydroxide, purity (98.0%) was obtained from (WinLab), perchloric acid (70%), chloroform, methanol (98.5%), ethanol (96.0%) and hydrochloric acid were purchased from BDH (England). Ribavirin capsules are labeled to contain 200 mg of RBV per capsule were purchased from local drug stores. Human plasma samples (Multi-Serum Normal, Randox Laboratories, UK) were obtained from commercial sources.

Apparatus :

The fluorescence intensity (FI) was measured on a Perkin-Elmer model LS-55 luminescence spectrometer (UK), equipped with a 150 W xenon arc lamp, grating excitation and emission monochromators and a Perkin-Elmer recorder. Slit widths for excitation and emission monochromators were set at 5.0 and 7.0 nm, respectively. A 1-cm quartz cell was used. Ultraspec-2100 pro, Ultra-visible spectrophotometer with matched 1-cm quartz cells was used for all spectrophotometric measurements. HANNA pH meter (Romania) was used for pH adjustments.

Standard solutions :

Ribavirin (RBV) standard solution :

Stock solution of ribavirin was prepared by dissolving an accurate amount (10.0 mg) of the drug in 100 mL of distilled water. Further dilution was carried out with water to obtain working solutions in the ranges of 0.05–10 and 5–100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for the spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods, respectively.

1,2-Naphthoquinone-4-sulphonate (NQS) solution :

Freshly prepared (NQS) solution was prepared daily by dissolving (150 mg) of NQS in 25 mL distilled water to obtain 0.6% (w/v). The solution was kept from light during use.

Calcium hydride solution :

Calcium hydride solution was prepared by dissolving (10.0 mg) of calcium hydride into 100 mL methanol to obtain a solution of 0.01% (w/v).

Sample solution of capsules :

The content of ten capsules were weighed and finely powdered. An accurate amount equivalent to 100 mg of RBV was transferred into a 100-mL volumetric flask, dissolved in about 50 mL of distilled water and sonicated for 5 min. Then the volume was completed with distilled water. The prepared solution was filtered and diluted quantitatively with distilled water to obtain a suitable concentration for the analysis.

Plasma samples :

Aliquots of different concentrations of RBV were added separately to 1.0 mL of plasma samples. The spiked plasma samples were treated with 0.1 mL of 70% perchloric acid and left to stand for 1 min. The samples were centrifuged for 20 min at 15000 rpm. The supernatants were transferred into test tubes and neutralized with 1.0 mol L^{-1} NaOH solution.

General procedures :

Spectrofluorometric method :

Aliquots of standard RBV solution (0.05–10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) were treated with 1.0 mL of both 0.01 mol L^{-1} NaOH and 1.0 mL of (0.6%, w/v) NQS reagent and heated in a water bath at 80 ± 5 °C for 60 min and then cooled in ice water for 2 min. The contents were extracted in separating funnels with two portions (5.0 mL) of chloroform.

The combined chloroformic extracts were evaporated under stream of air and the residues were reconstituted in 2.0 mL of methanol and quantitatively transferred into a 10-mL calibrated flask. A one milliliter of calcium hydride (CaH_2) solution (0.03%, w/v in methanol) was added and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 5 min at room temperature (25 ± 5 °C). The solution was diluted to volume with 0.025 mol L^{-1} ethanolic HCl and the fluorescence intensity of the resulting solution was measured at 406 nm after excitation at 344 nm against a reagent blank treated similarly.

Spectrophotometric method :

Aliquots of standard RBV solution (5–100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was treated with 1.0 mL of both 0.01 mol L^{-1} NaOH

and NQS reagent (0.6%, w/v) and then heated in a water bath at 80 ± 5 °C for 60 min and cooled in ice water for 2 min. The contents were extracted in separating funnels containing anhydrous sodium sulfate with two portions of (5.0 mL) of chloroform. The combined chloroformic extracts were transferred into 10-mL calibrated flasks and the solutions were completed to volume with chloroform if necessary. The absorbance of the resulting solutions were measured at 452 nm against a reagent blank treated similarly.

Stoichiometric studies :

The stoichiometric studies were carried out using Job's method of continuous variation¹⁴. Master equimolar (2.5×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹) aqueous solutions of RBV and NQS were prepared. Series of 5.0 mL portions of the master solutions of RBV and NQS were made up comprising different complementary proportions (0 : 10, 1 : 9, . . . , 9 : 1, 10 : 0, inclusive) in test tubes. Each tube was treated by 1.0 mL of 0.01 mol L⁻¹ NaOH and the procedure described in Spectrophotometric method section was then performed.

Results and discussion

Analytical spectra characteristics :

In the present study, NQS has been used as a fluorogenic and a chromogenic reagent for primary and secondary amines¹⁵. Therefore, NQS was used as a derivatizing reagent in the development of spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods for the determi-

nation of RBV in capsules and plasma. The reaction between RBV and NQS revealed that NQS-RBV orange colored product is exhibiting a maximum absorption at 452 nm and it is insoluble in water, but soluble in organic solvents. Since the present work was directed to involve plasma samples, the interference of endogenous amines was a major concern. It is well known that NQS reacts with the endogenous amines (e.g. amino acids) and yields water-soluble products¹⁶. For this reason, an extraction step was necessary for the development of selective methods for the determination of RBV in the presence of the endogenous amines. As well, the reduced RBV-NQS derivative was found to be fluorescent and exhibited emission maximum at 406 nm and excitation maximum at 344 nm. Scheme 1 shows the reaction pathway between RBV and NQS and Fig. 2a and 2b show the absorption, excitation, and emission spectra of the reaction product.

Method development :

Optimization of spectrofluorometric procedure :

To optimize the experimental conditions of the spectrofluorometric procedure, a reduction and a selective extraction steps for RBV-NQS product were necessary. This is essential to provide the required selectivity for analyzing the plasma samples as the NQS products with endogenous amines were water soluble. Based on the reported efficiency¹⁶, calcium hydride as a reducing reagent was selected for NQS derivatives. The effect of calcium hydride was studied by using different concentrations (0.001–0.01%, w/v). It was found that the high-

Scheme 1. The reaction pathway of ribavirin (RBV) with 1,2-naphthoquinone sulfonate (NQS).

Fig. 2. Absorption, excitation and emission spectra on the reaction products of RBV with NQS (0.06% w/v): (a) Absorption spectrum of the reaction product of RBV (50 μg mL⁻¹) with NQS after extraction with chloroform. (b) (1): Excitation and (2): emission spectra of the reduced reaction product.

est fluorescence intensity was achieved when the concentration was 0.003% in the final solution (1.0 mL of 0.03%, w/v). Using concentrations more than 0.003% did not affect the fluorescence intensity (Fig. 3). The effect of pH on the fluorescence intensity was also studied and the results showed that the highest fluorescence intensity was obtained at pH 4.0 (Fig. 4).

Optimization of spectrophotometric procedure :

For optimization the experimental conditions of the spectrophotometric method, the influence of different factors affecting the derivatization reaction were studied. Fig. 5a showed that the concentration of NQS affect the absorption intensity. The highest absorption intensity was recorded when the concentration of NQS was 0.06% (w/v) in the final solution (1 mL of 0.06% w/v). Moreover, Fig. 5b clarified that the optimum concentration of NaOH was 0.01 mol L⁻¹. The effect of temperature was investigated by carrying out the reaction at different temperatures (25–100 °C) and the maximum readings were at

Fig. 3. Effect of calcium hydride concentration on FI of reaction product of RBV (50 μg mL⁻¹) with NQS (0.06%, w/v).

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on the fluorescence intensity of the reduced reaction product of RBV-NQS.

Fig. 5. Effect of (a) NQS and (b) NaOH concentrations on the reaction of RBV (50 μg mL⁻¹).

60–90 °C, further experiments were carried out at 80 ± 5 °C. Also the effect of heating time on the derivatization reaction was tested at different times and the maximum absorption intensity was obtained after 60 min. It was found that the increase in heating time did not affect the absorption intensity (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Effect of heating time on reaction of RBV ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) with NQS.

Furthermore, the influence of different solvents were tested for dilution, methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylsulfoxide, iso-propanol and acetone. The highest readings were obtained when ethanol was used for dilution. As well, it was found that the colored RBV-NQS product is insoluble in the aqueous reaction medium. For measurements, the reaction product might be either dissolved in a miscible organic solvent of lower polarity than water reaction of RBV ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) with NQS or extracted with an immiscible extractive solvent. Different nonmiscible solvents were tested for the extraction of the RBV-NQS product: carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, dichloromethane, toluene and benzene. The highest readings were obtained when chloroform was used for extraction (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of diluting and extracting solvents on the intensity of the reaction product of RBV with NQS (0.06 w/v)

Diluting solvent	Spectrofluorometric method	Extracting solvent	Spectrophotometric method
	Fluorescence intensity		Absorbance
Methanol	253	Carbon tetrachloride	0.608
Ethanol	267	Chloroform	0.828
Acetonitrile	180	Dichloromethane	0.690
Dimethylsulfoxide	168	Toluene	0.333
Isopropanol	198	Benzene	0.179
Acetone	134		

Stoichiometric studies :

Job's method of continuous variation¹⁴ was employed. On studying the stoichiometric reaction between RBV and NQS, it was found that the ratio is 1 : 1 because RBV molecule contains only one center (primary amino group) available for the condensation reaction (Scheme 1).

Methods validation :

Linearity :

Under optimal experimental conditions for the proposed methods, linear calibration graphs were obtained in the range of $0.05\text{--}8.0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and $5.0\text{--}65.0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with correlation coefficients (0.9993 and 0.9999) for the spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods, respectively (Table 2).

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification LOQ :

Lower limit of detection (LOD) was determined by evaluating the lowest concentration of the analyte that could be readily detected. LOQ was determined by establishing the lowest concentration that could be measured. Both LOD and LOQ were calculated according to ICH Q2 (R1) recommendations¹⁷. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Quantitative parameters and statistical data for determination of ribavirin by the proposed spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods

Parameter	Spectrofluorometric method	Spectrophotometric method
Linear conc. range ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.05–8.0	5.0–65.0
Intercept (a) \pm SD _a	-0.184 ± 0.282	0.0112 ± 0.0055
Slope (b) \pm SD _b	39.920 ± 0.284	0.0123 ± 0.0014
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9993	0.9999
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	–	3.102×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	–	0.0127
LOD ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.0233	1.48
LOQ ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.0706	4.47
Robustness		
Ruggedness		
Regression equation : $A = a + bC$, a = intercept, b = slope, C = concentration ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), A = absorbance unit, SD _a = standard deviation of intercept and SD _b = standard deviation of slope.		

Precision and accuracy :

In order to investigate the precision of the proposed methods, five successive measurements of the sample solutions at three concentration levels of RBV were carried out. The results obtained as relative standard deviations (%RSDs) were 0.32–1.05% and 0.44–1.16 for the spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods, respectively (Table 3). From the recorded results, it was found that the proposed methods show good reproducibility. The precision of the proposed spectrofluorometric method was calculated in terms of intra-day and inter-day studies of spiked human plasma. The %RSD values of the recovery were 0.15–1.31 and 0.39–1.48% for the intra- and inter-assay determinations, respectively (Table 4).

Table 3. The precision of the proposed methods at three concentration levels of RBV

Method	Nominal concentration ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Found ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	%RSD ^a
Spectrofluorometric	1.0	0.97	1.05
	5.0	4.99	0.32
	7.0	6.96	0.58
Spectrophotometric	20	19.64	0.44
	40	39.62	59.98
	60	0.32	1.16

^aValues are mean of five determinations.

Table 4. The recovery studies for the proposed spectrofluorometric method for the determination of RBV in spiked human plasma

Taken ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Intra-assay		Inter-assay	
	Found ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Recovery % \pm RSD ^a	Found ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Recovery % \pm RSD ^a
0.10	0.990	99.00 \pm 0.49	0.998	99.80 \pm 0.58
0.20	0.199	99.50 \pm 0.15	0.200	100.00 \pm 0.71
0.40	0.387	96.75 \pm 1.31	0.402	100.50 \pm 1.25
0.60	0.589	98.16 \pm 0.53	0.598	99.67 \pm 1.48
0.80	0.798	98.63 \pm 0.39	0.779	97.38 \pm 0.86
1.20	1.210	100.83 \pm 0.52	1.202	100.16 \pm 0.39

^aValues are mean of three and five determinations for intra- and inter-assay determination.

The accuracy of the proposed methods was evaluated by applying the standard addition method. The obtained results were 99.52–99.81 \pm 0.41–1.17% indicating the high accuracy of the proposed methods. Moreover, the

accuracy of the proposed spectrofluorometric method was evaluated by the recovery studies of spiked human plasma samples. The obtained recovery values were 97.39–100.83 \pm 0.15–1.48 (Table 4).

Robustness and ruggedness :

To investigate the robustness of the proposed methods small variation of method variables was carried out. The influence of concentration of analytical reagents and reaction time were evaluated. The recovery percentage was calculated each time. It was found that small variation of methods variables did not significantly affect the procedures. Ruggedness was also tested by applying the proposed methods to the assay of RBV using the same operational conditions but using two different instruments and two different laboratories. Results obtained from lab-to-lab and day-to-day variations were found to be reproducible, the % recovery values were 98.80–100.20% and %RSD was 0.13–0.18% for the spectrophotometric and spectrofluorometric methods, respectively.

Interference studies :

The influence of interferences such as excipients (glucose, sucrose, lactose, starch, talc and magnesium stearate) that are commonly added to dosage forms was studied. The results obtained as percentage recoveries were 98.20–100.60%, indicating no interference were found. Furthermore, the influence of some amino acids such as (glycine, cystine, valine and leucine) was examined. The obtained results were 98.20–100.15% indicating that there is no interference for such amino acids with the proposed methods.

Analytical applications :

The proposed methods have been applied for the determination of RBV in bulk powder and its capsules. The results obtained were compared statistically with those obtained from the reported HPLC method¹⁸ in terms of accuracy (*t*-test) and precision (*F*-test). The percentage recoveries obtained were 99.17 \pm 0.70% and 99.66 \pm 0.48 for the spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods, respectively (Table 5). These experimental values clarified good agreement with no significant difference at 95% confidence limit.

Table 5. Analysis of RBV in capsules by the proposed and reported methods

Method	Recovery % \pm RSD	t-Value	F-Value
Spectrofluorometric	99.17 \pm 0.700	0.37 (2.23)*	3.60 (5.05)*
Spectrophotometric	99.66 \pm 0.48	1.16 (2.23)*	1.73 (5.05)*
Reported HPLC ¹⁸	99.37 \pm 0.37	-	-

Conclusion :

Selective, sensitive and accurate spectrofluorometric and spectrophotometric methods for the determination of RBV in bulk, capsules and plasma were developed. The proposed methods are advantageous when compared with the previously reported spectrophotometric or spectrofluorometric methods for analysis of RBV in terms of their selectivity and sensitivity. The results obtained in this study provide good agreements with those obtained by the reported method and no significant difference was observed. Moreover, the proposed methods were inexpensive, flexible and reproducible to be used for the routine analysis of RBV in quality control and clinical analysis.

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